

Random Samples Generation from Neutrosophic Distributions Using the `neutrostat` Package in R

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Abstract. Random sample generation plays a fundamental role in statistical simulation, model validation, and performance evaluation. In the context of neutrosophic statistics, where uncertainty, indeterminacy, and imprecision are explicitly modeled, generating random samples from neutrosophic probability distributions presents unique challenges. This work proposes a unified framework that simulates random samples from a variety of neutrosophic distributions using the "neutrostat" package in R. The package offers a set of user-friendly functions to generate neutrosophic random samples where each observation is represented by a neutrosophic observation with lower and upper bounds. Finally, we provide examples for some of the well-known classes of neutrosophic distributions including neutrosophic exponential, neutrosophic normal, and neutrosophic Weibull distributions. Furthermore, we study the uses of these obtained samples for neutrosophic data analysis and modeling. This proposed tool provides researchers and practitioners with a powerful resource in areas where uncertain, vague, and imprecise data are involved. Finally, some real situations and simulation results are shown to demonstrate how our tool is flexible and valuable.

Keywords: Random sample; uncertainty measure; neutrosophic probability; neutrosophic distribution; R package

1. Introduction

In classical statistics, random generation of samples is the cornerstone of simulation studies, statistics tests, and assessing the performance of statistical techniques[1]. In practice, these samples typically have one of several pre-specified probability distributions, such as the normal, exponential, Weibull, or poisson models. But in many practical problems, information is not necessarily exact or sharp but they are usually accompanied by some degree of hesitation, imprecision, or incompleteness[2, 3, 4]. In order to overcome this drawback, the

neutrosophic statistics theory which is an extension of classical and fuzzy statistics theory has been developed[5]. Neutrosophic system was modeled by Florentin Smarandache and adopted for handling uncertain and inconsistent information with truth(T), indeterminacy(I), and falsehood(F) components across many applied problems[6]. In neutrosophic statistics, observations are not only point values but may also be intervals, which are specific to the characteristic uncertainty and imprecision of the data[7]. So, simulation, model construction and new testing of statistical procedures under uncertainties require to generate such random samples from the neutrosophic probability distributions. Although its theoretical aspect has been developed extensively, the application of neutrosophic sample generation in statistical software environments is rare. In probability theory random variable and its probability distribution plays a significant role for modelling many real world scenarios[8]. A neutrosophic random variable that is an extension of classical random variable is considered when the uncertainty, imprecision and incompleteness is imposed to the space of outcomes[9]. While classic random variables provide us with exact numerical values for events with corresponding crisp probabilistic distribution[10]. Neutrosophic random variables can provide interval or triple values to an event, representing different degrees of certainty[11]. For instance, consider the time to failure of a mechanical component observed under uncertain conditions rather than stating that the failure time is exactly 10 hours, a neutrosophic random variable may express it as an interval like [9.5, 10.8] hours, indicating the degree of confidence in the observed range. Another example is in medical diagnostics, where the measurement of a biomarker in a patient may not be precise due to test variability and environmental factors; a neutrosophic random variable allows representing the biomarker level as [4.8, 6.2] units, acknowledging partial indeterminacy in the reading. The corresponding neutrosophic probabilistic model provide framework to assign probabilities to such uncertain outcomes, capturing the indeterminacy not addressed by classical distributions[12]. In the last years, several neutrosophic distributions have been defined to model such an approach, such as the neutrosophic normal, the neutrosophic exponential, the neutrosophic Laplace, the neutrosophic inverse gaussian, neutrosophic Burr distribuiton and the neutrosophic gamma-Lomax distributions [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. These developments enrich the toolbox necessary for simulation, inference, and decision in receiving environments where the classical assumption on the precision of the data can no longer be fulfilled. Although there are plenty of theoretical results involving neutrosophic random variables and neutrosophic probability distributions, however there is still a strong need for construction of a free and user-friendly R package that brings these theories to the real world applications. To fill this void, we develop here the neutrosophic framework for simulating random samples from neutrosophic distributions using the `neutrostat` package in R. It is constructed to give tools The `neutrostat` package is designed to provide tools for the

generation, summarization, and analysis of neutrosophic data, with special emphasis on ease of use, extensibility, and reproducibility. Cause along to randomize in both left bound and right bound or parameter a built-in functions to produce lower and upper sets of neutrosophic random samples of several well-known distributions. The primary purpose of this study is to provide to applied researchers and practitioners a versatile and user-friendly tool to operate with neutrosophic distributions under the R programming language environment. In light of the growing application of simulation-based studies to decision-making, reliability engineering, healthcare and social sciences, the problem of simulating uncertainty becomes more and more important. The package allows performing experiments and validations of statistical methodologies under different degree of indeterminacy, by means of a set of integrated simulation based tools. Moreover, the neutrosophic sample generation has other ramification for data analysis as it is crucial for the design of neutrosophic control charts, estimation techniques and model comparison frameworks where uncertainty is not negligible. For instance, when modeling lifetime or healthcare data with unknown system failure modes, or in environments with incomplete measurement instruments, neutrosophic distributions offer a more realistic representation compared to classical models. This paper contains extensive descriptions of the simulation functions, supplementing illustrative examples and code. The structure of the resulting neutrosophic data is studied in the context of interval-valued outputs, compatibility with neutrosophic parameters and unification with neutrosophic summary statistics. The effectiveness and generality of the proposed method are verified by the simulation results.

By illustrating in practice, the generation of neutrosophic random samples, the current work adds to the emerging field of computational neutrosophic statistics, and may promote future development of uncertainty-wise tools in statistical computing. Ultimately, this paper is to contribute towards the development of computational neutrosophic methods in so far as theory and application are concerned.

This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, some neutrosophic data and their algebraic operations are presented. In Section 3, the neutrostat package is described with some key functions for simulated data sets. Finally, the main findings of the work are concluded in Section 4.

2. Preliminaries and Theoretical Background

In practical conditions, observations are often imprecise, incomplete, or uncertain due to measurement errors, inherent vagueness, or conflicting sources. Conventional statistical distributional models, which rely on exact data information, may fail to capture the complexity of such environments. To address this, neutrosophic data were introduced based on the framework of neutrosophic algebraic operations, as proposed by Smarandache. Neutrosophic data

are characterized by the presence of three independent components: $[T, I, F]$, each typically ranging within the real standard or non-standard subsets of the interval $[0, 1]$.

Neutrosophic data refer to a collection of observations in which certain values are not precisely known and instead contain an indeterminate component. Such data may arise in both discrete and continuous contexts. An example of a discrete neutrosophic dataset is given as:

$$1, 4, 6, 5, 2 + \mathbb{I}_a, 9, 8 + \mathbb{I}_b$$

where \mathbb{I}_a and \mathbb{I}_b represent the indeterminacy components associated with numbers 2 and 8, respectively. For example, let $\mathbb{I}_a = [1.5, 2.5]$ and $\mathbb{I}_b = [0.5, 1.0]$. Then, the corresponding values become uncertain: the number $2 + \mathbb{I}_a$ may be within the range $[3.5, 4.5]$, and $8 + \mathbb{I}_b$ may lie within $[8.5, 9.0]$. This uncertainty reflects the imprecise nature of the data, where exact values are not fully known due to the presence of indeterminacy. In a general structure, a neutrosophic number can be expressed as:

$$N = C + \mathbb{I} \tag{1}$$

where C denotes the determinate (crisp) part of the observation, and I represents the indeterminate component, typically modeled as an interval or a range of possible values. With zero indeterminacy, Eq.(1) converts to classical dataset. Thus, a neutrosophic number holds a more generalized structure than traditional crisp numbers.

When working with data that contain neutrosophic values, arithmetic operations must be handled using interval arithmetic principles. Suppose we denote two neutrosophic interval numbers as $A = [a_L, a_U]$ and $B = [b_L, b_U]$, where $a_L, a_U, b_L, b_U \in \mathbb{R}$ and $a_L \leq a_U, b_L \leq b_U$. Let the binary operation \diamond represent a general arithmetic operation such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, or division. Then the operation can be defined as:

$$[a_L, a_U] \diamond [b_L, b_U] = [\gamma, \delta] \tag{2}$$

where

$$[\gamma, \delta] = \{A \diamond B \mid a_L \leq A \leq a_U, b_L \leq B \leq b_U\}.$$

In particular, these operations are evaluated as follows:

$$[a_L, a_U] + [b_L, b_U] = [a_L + b_L, a_U + b_U] \tag{3}$$

$$[a_L, a_U] - [b_L, b_U] = [a_L - b_U, a_U - b_L] \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{[a_L, a_U]}{[b_L, b_U]} = [a_L, a_U] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{b_U}, \frac{1}{b_L} \right], \quad \text{provided } 0 \notin [b_L, b_U] \tag{5}$$

$$[a_L, a_U] \cdot [b_L, b_U] = [\gamma, \delta] \quad (6)$$

where

$$\gamma = \min\{a_L b_L, a_L b_U, a_U b_L, a_U b_U\}, \quad \delta = \max\{a_L b_L, a_L b_U, a_U b_L, a_U b_U\}.$$

These rules ensure that the indeterminacy and variability inherent in neutrosophic data are properly managed during computation.

The expressions for multiplication and division of neutrosophic numbers can be further simplified when certain conditions about their bounds are known, such as $x_L > 0$, $y_U < 0$, $x_L < 0$, or $y_U < 0$.

To better understand the structure of neutrosophic numbers and how computations are performed with them, consider a practical example. Suppose a hydrologist monitored water levels (in centimeters) at a reservoir in Veszprem, Hungary, over a span of 10 days. The collected data reflect measurement uncertainties caused by equipment inconsistencies or incomplete recordings. As a result, some values are given as intervals representing possible ranges, while others are precise measurements from high-accuracy devices. The reported water levels for the 10 days are as follows:

$$30, [27, 29], 33, [31, 34], 28, 35, [32, 36], 30, [29, 31], [26, 28]$$

Applying the neutrosophic statistical definitions for mean, median, and standard deviation as outlined in the literature, we calculate the following descriptive summaries of the water level data:

$$\text{Neutrosophic Mean} = [30.1, 31.4]$$

$$\text{Neutrosophic Standard Deviation} = [1.72, 3.90]$$

These interval-based summary measures provide a more flexible and informative analysis compared to traditional crisp statistics, especially in scenarios involving uncertainty and imprecision in observational data.

It is important to highlight that the computations presented here strictly adhere to the foundational principles of neutrosophic numbers. Using the functions available in our **neutrostat** R package, such basic statistical measures can be calculated within seconds, even for larger neutrosophic datasets. The package is designed to efficiently process uncertain and imprecise data while maintaining computational accuracy. However, ensuring the validity of neutrosophic statistical results requires careful attention to the core operations and their theoretical extensions.

3. Overview of neutrostat

The `neutrostat` R package is a powerful computing tool for handling data under neutrosophic statistical theory that are uncertain, fuzzy and imprecise. Designed to cater for both theoretical research and practical modeling, the package contains utilities for calculating standard statistical indices, arithmetic operations with interval-valued data, and generating samples from neutrosophic probability distributions.

It supports several classical distributions extended into the neutrosophic domain, such as the neutrosophic exponential, gamma, Weibull, normal, Laplace, and Rayleigh distributions. Each distribution is equipped with functions for density evaluation, CDF, quantile function, random generation, and graphical visualization (PDF and CDF plots).

The `neutrostat` R also provides the fundamental summary statistics like neutrosophic mean, median, standard-deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis which makes it applicable for exploratory data analysis in the case of uncertainty. It fills the void and provides a practical and friendly framework due to the lack of statistical software to model neutrosophic data. The package is an easy-to-use software library for neutrosophic statistics intended to assist statistical analysis in an uncertain, obscure and vague sense by the concept of statistical neutrosophy. The package enables simulation and summary of neutrosophic data and extends traditional probability distributions into the neutrosophic domain. This includes built-in functionality for generating random samples, calculating probability density and cumulative distribution values, computing quantiles, and producing graphical outputs for distributions where values may be uncertain or interval-valued.

An important strength of `neutrostat` is its capability of processing complex and large neutrosophic datasets with efficient algorithms. This would allow researchers to surpass the abstraction of theory and to use the neutrosophic approach for practical processing of uncertain information in specific domains, such as engineering, medicine, economics, environmental, etc. The package also provides descriptive statistical tools to compute neutrosophic mean, median, standard deviation, variance, skewness, and kurtosis. Additionally, it supports interval arithmetic and offers helper functions for generating and analyzing uncertain values defined by lower and upper bounds or truth–indeterminacy–falsity components.

How to Install

The package can be installed the in two ways:

- **From CRAN:**

```
install.packages("neutrostat")
```

- **From GitHub (Development Version):**

```
# If not already installed:
install.packages("devtools")
devtools::install_github("kzst/neutrostat")
```

The core functions available in the package for various neutrosophic probability distributions are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Key Functions for Neutrosophic Distributions: Density, CDF, Quantile, Simulation, and Plotting Tools in the `neutrostat` R Package

Distribution Type	Density	CDF	Quantile	Random
Neutrosophic Exponential	<code>dnexp()</code>	<code>pnexp()</code>	<code>qnexp()</code>	<code>rnexp()</code>
Neutrosophic Gamma	<code>dngam()</code>	<code>pngam()</code>	<code>qngam()</code>	<code>rngam()</code>
Neutrosophic Normal	<code>dnnorm()</code>	<code>pnnorm()</code>	<code>qnnorm()</code>	<code>rnnorm()</code>
Neutrosophic Weibull	<code>dnwbl()</code>	<code>pnwbl()</code>	<code>qnwbl()</code>	<code>rnwbl()</code>
Neutrosophic Laplace	<code>dnlap()</code>	<code>pnlap()</code>	<code>qnlap()</code>	<code>rnlap()</code>
Neutrosophic Rayleigh	<code>dnray()</code>	<code>pnray()</code>	<code>qnray()</code>	<code>rnray()</code>

Table 1 presents a summary of the core functions available in the `neutrostat` R package for working with neutrosophic probability distributions. The package includes implementations for several widely used distributions extended into the neutrosophic framework. For each distribution, the table lists the functions used to calculate the probability density, cumulative distribution, and quantile values, as well as functions to generate random samples. Additionally, it includes plotting functions for visualizing the neutrosophic probability density function (PDF) and cumulative distribution function (CDF). The functions facilitate to simulate, estimate, and visualize uncertain or imprecise data in a structured and reproducible way. The uniform function naming allows also researchers and applied data analysts, who are working in the area of neutrosophic or neutrosophic statistics, using the package in a most intuitive way. The `neutrostat` R package includes functions for generating random samples and plotting the neutrosophic probability density and cumulative distribution functions. Below are example codes demonstrating the generation of random samples and visualizing distributions for various neutrosophic models.

TABLE 2. Random sample from Neutrosophic Exponential distribution

```
# Load the package
library(neutrostat)
# Samples Neutrosophic Exponential with neutrosophic rate parameter [0.5, 1.5]
set.seed(123)
samples <- rnexp(10, rate_l=0.5, rate_u=1.5, stats = TRUE)
print(samples)
```

The output of the Table 2 can be seen below:

```
$samples
      [,1]      [,2]
[1,] 2.1111006 6.3333017
[2,] 0.1926710 0.5780130
[3,] 0.4332294 1.2996883
[4,] 1.5017612 4.5052837
[5,] 2.2952969 6.8858906
[6,] 0.1475161 0.4425483
[7,] 0.1731588 0.5194764
[8,] 0.2346110 0.7038329
[9,] 0.0977485 0.2932455
[10,] 0.1413119 0.4239356
```

```
$stats
  Statistic Simulated_Value
1      Mean      0.733, 2.199
2       SD       0.88, 2.64
3       Q1       0.154, 0.462
4     Median     0.214, 0.641
5       Q3       1.235, 3.704
6 Skewness     0.986, 0.986
7 Kurtosis     2.176, 2.176
```

The `rnexp()` function is designed to generate random samples from the neutrosophic exponential distribution. An important argument in this function is `stats`, which controls the type of output returned.

- When `stats = FALSE` (the **default setting**), the function returns **only the random samples** drawn from the distribution. This is useful when the user is primarily interested in the generated data itself.
- When `stats = TRUE`, the function returns **both** the random samples and their **summary statistics**. These statistics typically include the neutrosophic mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for each generated sample.

Likewise, we can draw PDF, CDF, quantile values for the neutrosophic exponential distribution.

For example:

```
x <- c(1,1.5, 2) # Values at which to evaluate the PDF
```

```
rate_l <- 0.5
```

```
rate_u <- 1.5
```

```
dnexp(x, rate_l, rate_u)
```

output yielded:

```
      PDF_l    PDF_u
1 0.3032653 0.3346952
2 0.1580988 0.2361833
3 0.0746806 0.1839397
```

```
# CDF values
```

```
q <- c(1, 2, 3)
```

```
rate_l <- 0.5
```

```
rate_u <- 1.5
```

```
pnexp(q, rate_l, rate_u)
```

output yielded:

```
      CDF_l    CDF_u
1 0.3934693 0.7768698
2 0.6321206 0.9502129
3 0.7768698 0.9888910
```

```
p <- 0.1 # Probability at which to evaluate the
```

```
rate_l <- 0.5
```

```
rate_u <- 1.5
```

```
qnexp(p, rate_l, rate_u)
```

output yielded:

```
0.07024034 0.21072103
```

Moreover, the `plot()` function can be used to visualize the uncertainty in the neutrosophic exponential distribution by plotting its PDF and CDF. These plots display the range of possible curves resulting from the interval-valued rate parameter.

- For the PDF, the function plots the lower and upper bounds of the density curves corresponding to `rate_l` and `rate_u`, providing a shaded region that captures the neutrosophic uncertainty.
- For the CDF, the plot shows the cumulative probability bounds over the support of the distribution. This gives a visual representation of the spread caused by the uncertain rate parameter.

The complete PDF and CDF of the neutrosophic exponential distribution can be seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2 by using the functions below:

PDF plot can be drawn by:

```
plot_npdfexp(rate_l = 1.5, rate_u = 2, x = c(0, 4))
```

CDF plot can be drawn by:

```
plot_ncdfexp(rate_l = 1, rate_u = 2, x = c(0, 4))
```


FIGURE 1. The PDF curve of the neutrosophic exponential distribution

FIGURE 2. The CDF curve of the neutrosophic exponential distribution

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the basic plots of neutrosophic exponential distribution. The neutrosophic PDF and CDF is defined over an interval, reflecting the range of possible densities and cumulative probabilities for a given value of $x > 0$. For each point x , the PDF lies between the values obtained using $rate_l$ and $rate_u$. The shaded region in the PDF and CDF plot represents this band of imprecision. It visually captures the uncertainty in the density function and cumulative function due to the indeterminate rate parameter.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have proposed a practical approach for drawing random samples from neutrosophic probability distributions with the `neurostat` R package. The work presents a link between new theoretical developments in neutrosophic statistic and real world applications with computational tool for dealing with imprecise, indeterminate and inconsistent information. We illustrated how the `neurostat` package supports the study of neutrosophic data using illustrative examples and simulations in terms of the random generation, descriptive summary and visualization features. The importance of this contribution is to provide a standard and reproducible method to simulate data from neutrosophic distributions, an area that has remained largely theoretical until now. By allowing researchers to investigate the neutrosophic models computationally, this study aims to make the neutrosophic statistical techniques easily accessible to the broader academic community for applications in quality control, economics, healthcare, and decision science. By allowing researchers to do computational research on neutrosophic model, this work facilitates more and deeper applications of the neutrosophic statistical methods in quality control, economics, healthcare, decision science

and so on. Future possible directions include an extension of the package with other neutrosophic distributions, support of interval-valued estimates, as well as the implementation of advanced visualization and modeling techniques. Moreover, there is a strong need for collaborative efforts to promote best practices in neutrosophic computation, ensuring the reliability and interpretability of statistical results derived under uncertainty.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

The data used in this work is available within the manuscript.

References

1. Smarandache, F. Introduction to Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability, Neutrosophic Statistics and Their Applications to Decision Making. In **Neutrosophic Paradigms: Advancements in Decision Making and Statistical Analysis: Neutrosophic Principles for Handling Uncertainty*; Springer, 2025; pp. 3–21.
2. Das, S.; Roy, B.K.; Kar, M.B.; Kar, S.; Pamučar, D. Neutrosophic fuzzy set and its application in decision making. **Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* 2020, 11, 5017–5029.
3. Smarandache, F.; Khan, Z. *Neutrosophic Paradigms: Advancements in Decision Making and Statistical Analysis*; Springer.
4. Khan, Z.; Krebs, K.L. Enhancing Neutrosophic Data Analysis: A Review of Neutrosophic Measures and Applications with Neutrostat. **Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2025, 78, 181–190.
5. Smarandache, F.; Vladutescu, S.; Colhon, M.; Al-Omeri, W.; Jafari, S.; Khan, M.Z.; Khan, M.F.; Aslam, M.; Mughal, A.R. *New Challenges in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications*; MDPI, 2020.
6. Patro, S.K.; Smarandache, F. *The Neutrosophic Statistical Distribution, More Problems, More Solutions*; Infinite Study, 2016.
7. AlAita, A.; Aslam, M. Analysis of covariance under neutrosophic statistics. *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation* 2023, 93(3), 397–415; Taylor & Francis.
8. Huang, C.; Mi, X.; Kang, B. Basic probability assignment to probability distribution function based on the Shapley value approach. **International Journal of Intelligent Systems* 2021, 36(8), 4210–4236; Wiley Online Library.
9. Zeina, M.B.; Hatip, A. Neutrosophic random variables. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2021, 39, 44–52; *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*.
10. Jdid, M.; Alhabib, R.; Salama, A.A. The basics of neutrosophic simulation for converting random numbers associated with a uniform probability distribution into random variables follow an exponential distribution. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2023, 53, 358–366.
11. Khan, Z.; Al-Bossly, A.; Almazah, M.M.A.; Alduais, F.S. On statistical development of neutrosophic gamma distribution with applications to complex data analysis. *Complexity* 2021, 2021(1), 3701236; Wiley Online Library.
12. Granados, C.; Das, A.K.; Das, B. Some continuous neutrosophic distributions with neutrosophic parameters based on neutrosophic random variables. *Advances in the Theory of Nonlinear Analysis and its Application* 2022, 6(3), 380–389.

13. Al-Essa, L.A.; Jamal, F.; Shafiq, S.; Khan, S.; Abbas, Q.; Khan Sherwani, R.A.; Aslam, M. Properties and Applications of Neutrosophic Burr XII Distribution. *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems* 2025, 18(1), 10.
14. Sherwani, R.A.K.; Aslam, M.; Raza, M.A.; Farooq, M.; Abid, M.; Tahir, M. Neutrosophic normal probability distribution—a spine of parametric neutrosophic statistical tests: properties and applications. *Neutrosophic Operational Research: Methods and Applications* 2021, 153–169; Springer.
15. Duan, W.Q.; Khan, Z.; Gulistan, M.; Khurshid, A. Neutrosophic exponential distribution: modeling and applications for complex data analysis. *Complexity* 2021, 2021(1), 5970613; Wiley Online Library.
16. Ibrahim, A.M.M.; Khan, Z. Neutrosophic Laplace Distribution with Properties and Applications in Decision Making. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science (IJNS)* 2024, 23(1).
17. Ibrahim, M.M.; Khan, Z.; et al. Neutrosophic Inverse Gaussian Distribution in Economic Policy Design under Indeterminacy. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 2025, 82(1), 31.
18. Khan, Z.; Amin, A.; Lane-Krebs, K. Neutrosophic Lomax Distribution with Application in Decision-Making Problems. In *Neutrosophic Paradigms: Advancements in Decision Making and Statistical Analysis: Neutrosophic Principles for Handling Uncertainty*; Springer, 2025; pp. 235–254.
19. Alamri, F.S.; Aslam, M. Data Generation and Application Using the Neutrosophic Erlang Distribution. **Journal of Big Data** 2025, 12(1), 48.
20. Smarandache, F. *Introduction to Neutrosophic Statistics*; Infinite Study, 2013.

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